

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Bayesian conjugate analysis for federated statistical inference

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Abstract

In many research settings, sufficiently large sample sizes can only be achieved by combining data from multiple collection sites. However, pooling individual participant data in a central server is often restricted due to regulatory constraints. Federated inference addresses this challenge by distributing the statistical analysis across local sites, allowing pooled inference in a central server using privacy-preserving summary statistics. Although federated inference methods exist in a frequentist framework, the full potential of Bayesian approaches has not yet been explored. Bayesian methods offer distinct advantages, including the ability to incorporate prior knowledge and perform predictive checks for model criticism. A recently published Bayesian method for federated inference relies on approximate solutions even in linear regression scenarios where exact solutions are available. We therefore propose a different approach to federated inference using Bayesian conjugate analysis (BCA), which is communication-efficient and mathematically convenient. For linear regression problems, BCA yields lossless parameter inference, that is, producing the same posterior distribution as if the pooled data had been analyzed. For problems where the parameters estimates are asymptotically normal (such as generalized linear models), BCA is equivalent to a multivariate fixed-effects meta-analysis, up to prior specification. We further show that BCA naturally lends itself to Reverse-Bayes analysis, which allows for computationally efficient predictive checks and identification of outlier sites. An implementation of BCA is available through the open-source `confeR` package (conjugate federated analysis in R). Our proposed framework thus facilitates privacy-preserving multi-center trials in a Bayesian setting.

Highlights

What is already known

- Privacy-preserving distributed algorithms for federated inference have been developed using a frequentist surrogate likelihood approach.
- In the Bayesian framework, an approximate algorithm for federated inference has recently been developed for generalized linear and survival models.

What is new

- We derive a lossless one-shot solution for linear models using Bayesian conjugate priors and an approximate one-shot algorithm for models with asymptotically normal parameter estimates, such as generalized linear models.
- We derive corresponding Reverse-Bayes formulas and demonstrate their utility for prior predictive checks, heterogeneity assessment, and outlier identification.

Potential impact for readers

- Our proposed framework facilitates privacy-preserving multi-center trials for researchers who want to leverage the benefits of Bayesian statistics.
- Our method is freely available from the open-source `confeR` package (conjugate federated analysis in R), including Reverse-Bayes analysis and visualization using multivariate forest plots.

1. Introduction

In many modern research problems across biomedicine and social science, sufficiently large sample sizes can only be achieved by pooling data from multiple studies or collection sites.^{1,2} However, pooling individual participant data (IPD) in a central server may be restricted due to privacy, regulatory, or logistical constraints. We define *federated inference* as the problem setting in which pooled parameter estimation is desired, but local data sets from different sites (e.g., hospitals) cannot be merged. Therefore, instead of centralizing the data, each site locally computes privacy-preserving summary statistics according to a shared analysis protocol, which are then transmitted to a central server for pooled parameter estimation (Figure 1). This setup is conceptually similar to distributed computing for large-scale data, where a massive data set is partitioned across compute nodes, processed independently, and then the local results aggregated to obtain a global result. In both cases, the full inference procedure is coordinated across multiple nodes or sites using a shared analysis protocol, despite the data being physically separated.

The ideal outcome of a federated inference method is a *lossless* estimation of statistical parameters, that is, producing the same estimates and confidence intervals as would be obtained from the pooled data. In practical scenarios, federated inference methods should also be *communication-efficient*, for example, by supporting properties such as *one-shot execution* and *parallelization*. A one-shot procedure requires only a single round of communication between the local sites and the central server, in contrast to iterative procedures. A parallelizable method allows each local site to transmit its summary data independently, avoiding communication with the other sites. The utility of these properties depends on how the federated inference method is implemented. To demonstrate this, we consider a scenario with L local sites, where the time required to perform the local analysis in site $l \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, L\}$ is t_l . In a sequential procedure, the total time required for the federated inference is $\sum_{l=1}^L t_l$, whereas in a parallel procedure, it is reduced to $\max(t_1, \dots, t_L)$. If the federated inference is conducted using inter-human communication, t_l may be considerable, and therefore parallelization and one-shot execution become essential. On the other hand, if each local site is already connected to a pre-configured, automated network for federated inference, t_l may be small and iterative procedures more viable. However, establishing the infrastructure for such a network can also involve significant logistical and administrative challenges.

In federated inference problems, the data may not be homogeneously distributed across the local sites. Samples collected in different sites may come from different subpopulations, requiring a heterogeneity-aware statistical approach.^{3,4} Common approaches include *fixed-effects* and *random-effects* models. In a fixed-effects model, heterogeneity is characterized by unrelated site-specific effects.⁵ In contrast, a random-effects model assumes that site-specific effects follow an underlying probability distribution. The case of no heterogeneity is covered by the *common-effect* model (or fixed-effect model, note the singular), which assumes that all sites estimate the same true effect, subject only to sampling variability.

2. Review of methods for federated inference

Perhaps the best-known approach for combining inference results from multiple data sets is (univariate) meta-analysis,⁶ where an overall effect estimate is synthesized from individual estimates reported by separate studies. However, since these studies are typically conducted independently and without coordination, classical meta-analysis is not considered a form of federated inference. Although meta-analytic techniques can, in principle, be applied to true federated inference settings, more informative methods that can make use of additional quantities are often available (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Schematic representation of classical meta-analysis and federated inference. In classical meta-analysis, the published literature is systematically reviewed to synthesize effect estimates published by independent investigators (here: local sites). In federated inference, coordination between local sites enables more information to be shared while keeping the individual participant data private.

One example involves the joint estimation of multiple, correlated outcomes (such as measurements of systolic and diastolic blood pressure from the same patients) across multiple studies. In this case, meta-analysis should be performed in a multivariate manner,⁷ which requires the calculation of within-study correlations from IPD. In a classical meta-analysis where the studies are obtained from a systematic literature review, correlations or IPD may not always be available. However, in a federated meta-analysis, calculation of within-study correlations can be incorporated in the shared analysis protocol and transmitted to the central server while keeping the IPD private.

Going beyond meta-analytic techniques, a recent review article discusses a toolbox for federated learning named privacy-preserving distributed algorithms (PDA).² The collection of algorithms is implemented in the `pda` R package and supports continuous, binary, time-to-event, and count outcomes. Among these, the distributed linear mixed model (DLMM) algorithm is a lossless one-shot procedure for continuous outcomes.⁸ The one-shot privacy-preserving distributed algorithm to perform logistic regression (ODAL) is not lossless but achieves superior performance to meta-analytic techniques.⁹ The ODAL algorithm is based on a frequentist approach that extends the surrogate likelihood framework by Jordan, Lee, and Yang.^{10;3} The surrogate likelihood approximates the higher-order derivatives of the global likelihood by using the likelihood function of a local site as a “surrogate”. This approach results in a communication-efficient one-shot procedure.

Moving on to Bayesian frameworks, one approach to federated inference is consensus Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC).¹¹ In this setting, each site locally samples the posterior distribution and transmits the results to the central server, where a global posterior distribution is approximated. MCMC methods can be computationally expensive and are subject to Monte Carlo simulation error. For the problems discussed in this paper, we focus instead on analytic methods which do not require simulation.

A Bayesian example of such an analytic framework is the Bayesian Federated Inference (BFI) method recently proposed by Jonker, Pazira, and Coolen.^{12;13} The BFI estimator of the model parameters is

derived in two steps. First, the log posterior density for the combined data set is written in terms of the log posterior densities of the local sites. Second, these local densities are approximated by a second-order Taylor expansion around the maximum a posteriori (MAP) estimators. Originally developed for generalized linear models (GLMs) and later extended to survival models,¹⁴ BFI offers a one-shot algorithm and is implemented in the BFI R package; however, it is not lossless, even for ordinary linear models.

In this article, we investigate Bayesian conjugate analysis (BCA) as an alternative approach to federated inference for models with asymptotically normal parameter estimates, such as GLMs. We begin by applying BCA in a sequential manner (that is, transmitting summary statistics between sites) and show that the resulting formulas can be effectively implemented as a parallelized one-shot procedure. We further show that, in homogeneous settings, this approach is identical to a multivariate fixed-effect meta-analysis (up to prior specification) and to the BFI estimator. Notably, for the special case of linear regression, BCA achieves lossless inference, unlike BFI. Moreover, we demonstrate that Bayesian inference naturally lends itself to predictive checking using Reverse-Bayes analysis.¹⁵ This enables computationally efficient cross-validation of predictive performance and assessment of conflicts among the estimates obtained from the individual sites. Assessing heterogeneity is an important step in model selection and the identification of outlier sites.

The remainder of this article is structured as follows. Section 3 introduces Bayesian conjugate analysis to address the problem of federated inference. Section 4 derives the corresponding Reverse-Bayes formulas and shows how they can be used for outlier assessment. Section 5 describes the data sets used to compare Bayesian conjugate analysis with existing methods for federated inference. The results of these comparisons are presented in Section 6, followed by a discussion of the findings and their implications in Section 7.

3. Bayesian conjugate analysis for federated inference

Suppose data sets from L different local sites are available. The problem of federated inference precludes the direct combination of individual data sets, but each local site can transmit summary statistics to a central server for pooled parameter estimation. Let n_l be the sample size of local site l , such that the total sample size is $n = \sum_{l=1}^L n_l$. Each local site collects data $z_l = \{\mathbf{X}_l, \mathbf{y}_l\}$, with covariate matrix \mathbf{X}_l and outcome vector \mathbf{y}_l . Although the theory developed in this section is applicable to any model with asymptotically normal parameter estimates, we will focus on generalized linear models (GLM) as a key example. The GLM assumes a relationship of the form

$$E[\mathbf{y} | \mathbf{X}] = g^{-1}(\mathbf{X}\boldsymbol{\beta}),$$

where g^{-1} is the inverse of the link function $g(\cdot)$ and $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ is the vector of regression coefficients. To include an intercept term (β_0), the covariate matrix can be prepended with a column of 1s, such that $\mathbf{X}_l \in \mathbb{R}^{n_l \times (1+m)}$ and $\boldsymbol{\beta} \in \mathbb{R}^{1+m}$, where m is the number of covariates. The goal of federated inference is to estimate $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ and its uncertainty using only privacy-preserving summary statistics provided by the local sites. The maximum likelihood estimator of the GLM regression parameter $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ is asymptotically normal. Thus, in a Bayesian setting, we can approximate the likelihood with a normal distribution. This allows us to use well-understood *conjugate* priors.¹⁶ A conjugate prior has the property that the resulting posterior distribution belongs to the same probability distribution family as the prior distribution.

In Section 3.1, we derive a BCA procedure to address the problem of federated inference for models with normally distributed parameter estimates and known precision. This case serves as an approximation for GLMs, which we demonstrate using a logistic regression problem in Section 6.1. In Section 3.2, we consider the special case of linear regression (dropping the assumption of known precision), in which case the likelihood function is a normal distribution and no approximation is necessary. We show that

BCA on federated data yields a one-shot solution that, for uninformative priors, is equivalent to the ordinary least squares estimator on the combined data. We apply this procedure in Section 6.2. We note that the same formulas can also be used for Bayesian analyses with informative priors.

3.1. Normal model, known precision

We begin by reviewing a well-known result from Bayesian inference. Let $L(\boldsymbol{\mu})$ denote the likelihood function of an observation \mathbf{X} from a multivariate normal distribution $N_{m+1}(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma})$. The unknown mean vector $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ is a vector of dimension $m + 1$, while the covariance matrix $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$ is assumed to be known. The conjugate prior for this likelihood is a normal distribution with mean vector $\boldsymbol{\nu}$ and covariance matrix \boldsymbol{T} , i.e. $\boldsymbol{\mu} \sim N_{m+1}(\boldsymbol{\nu}, \boldsymbol{T})$. For simplicity of notation, we define the *precisions* (inverse covariance matrices) as $\boldsymbol{\Lambda} = \boldsymbol{\Sigma}^{-1}$ and $\boldsymbol{\Omega} = \boldsymbol{T}^{-1}$. Then, it can be shown¹⁶ that the posterior distribution takes the following form:

$$\boldsymbol{\mu} \mid \mathbf{X} \sim N_{m+1} \left((\boldsymbol{\Lambda} + \boldsymbol{\Omega})^{-1} (\boldsymbol{\Lambda} \mathbf{X} + \boldsymbol{\Omega} \boldsymbol{\nu}), (\boldsymbol{\Lambda} + \boldsymbol{\Omega})^{-1} \right). \quad (3.1)$$

We now return to the problem of federated inference with data sets from L local sites. First, each site performs a GLM regression to obtain local estimates for the regression coefficients $\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_l$ and the covariance matrix $\hat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_l$. As before, we also define the precision matrix $\hat{\boldsymbol{\Lambda}}_l = (\hat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_l)^{-1}$. Next, we apply Equation 3.1 sequentially from site 1 to L , using the posterior parameters from site l as the prior parameters for site $l + 1$. For this, we use the following variable substitutions:

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\mu} &\rightarrow \boldsymbol{\beta} \\ \mathbf{X} &\rightarrow \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{l+1} \\ \boldsymbol{\Lambda} &\rightarrow \hat{\boldsymbol{\Lambda}}_{l+1} \\ \boldsymbol{\nu} &\rightarrow \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_l \\ \boldsymbol{\Omega} &\rightarrow \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Lambda}}_l, \end{aligned}$$

where parameters with a tilde denote posterior estimates and parameters with a hat denote local estimates. For now, we use a flat prior for site 1, such that its posterior is given by the local parameter estimates plugged into the normal posterior (other priors are discussed below). In summary, we end up with the following procedure:

1. $\boldsymbol{\beta} \mid l_1 \sim N(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_1, \hat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_1)$,
2. $\boldsymbol{\beta} \mid l_1, l_2 \sim N(\tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_2, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_2)$
 where $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_2 = (\hat{\boldsymbol{\Lambda}}_1 + \hat{\boldsymbol{\Lambda}}_2)^{-1}$
 and $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_2 = \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_2 (\hat{\boldsymbol{\Lambda}}_1 \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_1 + \hat{\boldsymbol{\Lambda}}_2 \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_2)$,
3. $\boldsymbol{\beta} \mid l_1, l_2, l_3 \sim N(\tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_3, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_3)$
 where $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_3 = (\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Lambda}}_2 + \hat{\boldsymbol{\Lambda}}_3)^{-1} = (\hat{\boldsymbol{\Lambda}}_1 + \hat{\boldsymbol{\Lambda}}_2 + \hat{\boldsymbol{\Lambda}}_3)^{-1}$
 and $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_3 = \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_3 (\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Lambda}}_2 \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_2 + \hat{\boldsymbol{\Lambda}}_3 \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_3) = \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_3 (\hat{\boldsymbol{\Lambda}}_1 \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_1 + \hat{\boldsymbol{\Lambda}}_2 \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_2 + \hat{\boldsymbol{\Lambda}}_3 \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_3)$,
- \vdots
- L . $\boldsymbol{\beta} \mid l_1, \dots, l_L \sim N(\tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_L, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_L)$.

The notation $\beta | l_1, \dots, l_k$ denotes the posterior distribution of β given the data from local sites 1 to k . It can be easily shown by induction that the parameters $\tilde{\beta}_L$ and $\tilde{\Sigma}_L$ for the final posterior distribution are given by the following one-shot formulas:

$$\tilde{\Sigma}_L = \left(\sum_{l=1}^L \hat{\Lambda}_l \right)^{-1} \quad (3.2a)$$

$$\tilde{\beta}_L = \tilde{\Sigma}_L \sum_{l=1}^L \hat{\Lambda}_l \hat{\beta}_l. \quad (3.2b)$$

Therefore, the sequential updating scheme can be effectively implemented as a parallel procedure. Furthermore, because of the commutativity of matrix summation, the order of the local sites is irrelevant. It is also possible to use more informative priors with non-zero parameters Λ_0, β_0 for the first site. Conceptually, this is equivalent to adding a hypothetical site with index 0. Thus, the formulas in Equation 3.2 retain the same form, except that the summation symbols now run from 0 to L .

We further note that Equation 3.2 is mathematically equivalent to a multivariate fixed-effect meta-analysis,¹⁷ albeit applied in a different context. In a typical meta-analysis, the goal is to combine effect sizes from different studies, whereas here we combine regression parameters from different local sites. Finally, we note that this estimator is essentially identical to the BFI estimator for homogeneous settings, see Equation 7 in Jonker, Pazira, and Coolen.¹² The only difference is that the implementation of the BFI method requires a non-zero prior precision matrix of the form

$$\Lambda_0 = \Lambda - \sum_{l=1}^L \Lambda_l,$$

where Λ represents the combined data set prior and Λ_l represents the local site prior. In our assessment of the BFI methodology, we will use the scalar matrix $\Lambda = \Lambda_l = \lambda \mathbb{I}$ with $\lambda = 0.1$ to reproduce the analysis by the BFI authors. In the BCA approach, the same Λ_0 prior can in principle be used for the first site, thus recovering the BFI estimator. The parameter λ serves as a regularizer that shrinks the regression estimates towards 0 as λ increases. Choosing site-specific values for λ_l can thus be used to reduce overfitting for sites with small sample sizes.

3.2. Linear regression

For the special case of linear regression, an exact analytic solution to the problem of federated inference can be derived from Bayesian updating, avoiding the need for a normal approximation. Let us first consider the case of the combined data $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times (1+m)}$, $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^n$. We note that $\{\mathbf{X}^\top \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}^\top \mathbf{y}\}$ is a *sufficient statistic* for the linear regression parameter β ,¹⁸ which means that the statistic contains all the information the data set provides about the parameter. As we will show, additionally we only need to know $\mathbf{y}^\top \mathbf{y}$ and n to estimate the covariance matrix Σ as well. Thus, by transmitting the sufficient statistic $t(\mathbf{z}) = \{\mathbf{X}^\top \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}^\top \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{y}^\top \mathbf{y}, n\}$, it is possible to perform ordinary linear regression without access to the original data. It follows that a federated inference scenario introduces no information loss compared to performing linear regression on the combined data. To show this explicitly, we first recall the conjugate prior for Bayesian linear regression, which is a multivariate normal-gamma distribution:

$$p(\beta, \tau | \beta_0, \Lambda_0, a_0, b_0) = N(\beta | \beta_0, (\tau \Lambda_0)^{-1}) \times \text{Gamma}(\tau | a_0, b_0).$$

This prior depends on the four hyperparameters $\boldsymbol{\beta}_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{1+m}$, $\boldsymbol{\Lambda}_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{(1+m) \times (1+m)}$, $a_0 > 0$ and $b_0 > 0$. The parameter $\tau = \sigma^{-2}$ represents the inverse of the residual variance. Due to conjugacy, the posterior is again normal-gamma with updated hyperparameters:¹⁹

$$p(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \tau | \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{y}) = N(\boldsymbol{\beta} | \boldsymbol{\beta}_n, (\tau \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_n)^{-1}) \times \text{Gamma}(\tau | a_n, b_n),$$

where

$$\boldsymbol{\beta}_n = \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_n^{-1} (\boldsymbol{\Lambda}_0 \boldsymbol{\beta}_0 + \mathbf{X}^\top \mathbf{y}) \quad (3.3a)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\Lambda}_n = \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_0 + \mathbf{X}^\top \mathbf{X} \quad (3.3b)$$

$$a_n = a_0 + n/2 \quad (3.3c)$$

$$b_n = b_0 + \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{y}^\top \mathbf{y} + \boldsymbol{\beta}_0^\top \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_0 \boldsymbol{\beta}_0 - \boldsymbol{\beta}_n^\top \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_n \boldsymbol{\beta}_n). \quad (3.3d)$$

We now return to the problem of federated inference with L local data sets. Thus, we again apply a sequential updating procedure, where the posterior parameters from site l are used as the prior parameters for site $l + 1$. From Equations 3.3, we see that each local site needs to transmit four quantities: $\{\mathbf{X}_l^\top \mathbf{X}_l, \mathbf{X}_l^\top \mathbf{y}_l, \mathbf{y}_l^\top \mathbf{y}_l, n_l\}$. It is straightforward to prove by induction that sequential application of Equations 3.3 yields the following parallel one-shot formulas for the final posterior of site L :

$$\boldsymbol{\beta}_L = \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_L^{-1} (\boldsymbol{\Lambda}_0 \boldsymbol{\beta}_0 + \sum_{l=1}^L \mathbf{X}_l^\top \mathbf{y}_l) \quad (3.4a)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\Lambda}_L = \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_0 + \sum_{l=1}^L \mathbf{X}_l^\top \mathbf{X}_l \quad (3.4b)$$

$$a_L = a_0 + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{l=1}^L n_l \quad (3.4c)$$

$$b_L = b_0 + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{l=1}^L \mathbf{y}_l^\top \mathbf{y}_l + \frac{1}{2} (\boldsymbol{\beta}_0^\top \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_0 \boldsymbol{\beta}_0 - \boldsymbol{\beta}_L^\top \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_L \boldsymbol{\beta}_L). \quad (3.4d)$$

We can use prior knowledge to determine appropriate values for the prior hyperparameters $(\boldsymbol{\beta}_0, \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_0, a_0, b_0)$ of the first local site. If prior knowledge is not available, we can use a non-informative *reference prior*²⁰ to maximize the influence of the data on the posterior. Following Appendix A in Bernardo and Smith,¹⁸ we can set

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\beta}_0 &= \mathbf{0}_{m+1} \\ \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_0 &= \mathbf{0}_{(m+1) \times (m+1)} \\ a_0 &= -(m+1)/2 \\ b_0 &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

to obtain an improper, non-informative prior for the linear model. Although, technically, the gamma distribution is not defined for $a < 0$, the posterior distribution resulting from this reference prior is

proper, provided that $\mathbf{X}_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{m+1}$ is of rank $m+1$ and $n_1 > m+1$.²¹ Therefore, we apply this prior to Equation 3.4 to yield the following parallel one-shot formulas:

$$\boldsymbol{\beta}_L = \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_L^{-1} \left(\sum_{l=1}^L \mathbf{X}_l^\top \mathbf{y}_l \right) \quad (3.6a)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\Lambda}_L = \sum_{l=1}^L \mathbf{X}_l^\top \mathbf{X}_l \quad (3.6b)$$

$$a_L = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{l=1}^L n_l - \frac{m+1}{2} = \frac{n-m-1}{2} \quad (3.6c)$$

$$b_L = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{l=1}^L \mathbf{y}_l^\top \mathbf{y}_l - \frac{1}{2} (\boldsymbol{\beta}_L^\top \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_L \boldsymbol{\beta}_L). \quad (3.6d)$$

The maximum a posteriori (MAP) estimate for $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_L$ is given by $\boldsymbol{\beta}_L$. To get $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_L$, we use the mean of the marginal gamma distribution, $\tau_L = a_L/b_L$. In Appendix A, we show that $\sigma_L^2 = \tau_L^{-1}$ is equivalent to the residual variance of the ordinary least squares model for the combined data. Thus, our final parameter estimates are:

$$\tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_L = \boldsymbol{\beta}_L \quad (3.7)$$

$$\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_L = (\tau_L \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_L)^{-1}. \quad (3.8)$$

We further observe that Equations 3.6a and 3.6b yield the ordinary least squares estimator for the combined data:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_L &= \left(\sum_{l=1}^L \mathbf{X}_l^\top \mathbf{X}_l \right)^{-1} \sum_{l=1}^L \mathbf{X}_l^\top \mathbf{y}_l \\ &= (\mathbf{X}^\top \mathbf{X})^{-1} (\mathbf{X}^\top \mathbf{y}) \\ &= \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{\text{Combined}}. \end{aligned}$$

The second equality results from elementary matrix multiplication rules and the fact that the combined data can be constructed by concatenating the local data: $\mathbf{X}^\top = [\mathbf{X}_1^\top, \dots, \mathbf{X}_L^\top]$ and $\mathbf{y}^\top = [\mathbf{y}_1^\top, \dots, \mathbf{y}_L^\top]$.

3.2.1. Accounting for site-specific covariates

Regression coefficients for covariates that do not vary within a site cannot be estimated in a local linear regression model because their effects are absorbed into the site-specific intercept. An example of such a covariate may be the fraction of female nurses within a hospital. In a federated scenario, site-specific covariates can be easily included in the Bayesian updating scheme. Numeric covariates can be directly included in the covariate matrix \mathbf{X}_l without issue. Categorical covariates can be included using dummy variables. As an example, we consider the site identity itself as a site-specific categorical covariate. That is, we consider an intercept term for each site, rather than using a global intercept. Thus, we have $\boldsymbol{\beta}_l \in \mathbb{R}^{L+m}$ and $\mathbf{X}_l \in \mathbb{R}^{n_l \times (L+m)}$. Importantly, in the sequential updating scheme, each local site only modifies its own intercept term. Let $\mathbf{X}_l^* \in \mathbb{R}^{n_l \times m}$ be the “raw” covariate matrix for the l -th site without any intercept terms. Then, we construct our extended covariate matrix by concatenation:

$$\mathbf{X}_l = [\mathbb{1}_l, \mathbf{X}_l^*],$$

where $\mathbb{1}_l \in \mathbb{R}^{n_l \times L}$ is a matrix with 1s in the l -th column and 0 else. The remainder of the sequential updating scheme proceeds as in the homogeneous setting.

3.2.2. Accounting for site-specific residual variances

Similarly to the previous section, it is also possible to allow the residual variance σ^2 to vary between sites. To do so, we update only β and Λ sequentially. The hyperparameters a_l and b_l are updated for each site independently using the same priors a_0 and b_0 for each site. Note that this is equivalent to each site transmitting a locally computed σ^2 using ordinary linear regression. Computing the site-specific residual variances from the transmitted summary statistics at the central server simply avoids the need for local computation.

4. Reverse-Bayes for prior predictive checks

The parallel one-shot formulas in Equations 3.2 and 3.6 naturally lend themselves to Reverse-Bayes analysis.¹⁵ The basic idea is to reverse Bayes' theorem and derive the prior distribution from a given posterior. In a federated inference scenario, we can use Reverse-Bayes to remove the influence of the l -th local site from the posterior obtained from all L sites. We denote the reduced posterior by the index $-l$ (meaning all sites except site l). The same reduced posterior can also be computed using the standard Forward-Bayes approach by simply removing the l -th site from the computation. The key difference is that the Reverse-Bayes method requires fewer computational steps, which can be advantageous when working with many large datasets.

The reduced posterior can be used for cross-validation of predictive performance or to assess the influence of individual sites and identify potential outliers. However, since assessing predictive performance requires access to individual participant data (IPD), in privacy-preserving scenarios it is only possible with an additional round of communication between the central server and the local sites. In Section 4.3, we focus on outlier detection, which does not require access to IPD. To do so, we first need to derive the Reverse-Bayes formulas for the normal model and the linear model.

4.1. Normal model, known precision

To derive the Reverse-Bayes formulas for the reduced posterior parameters indexed by $-l$, we start with the corresponding Forward-Bayes formulas without the l -th site. In the federated inference scenario, this simply means summing over all sites except l . Then, we perform basic algebraic manipulations to express the Forward-Bayes formula as a function of the full parameters indexed by L and the local parameters indexed by l . In the case of the normal model with known precision, the Reverse-Bayes formulas can be immediately deduced from Equation 3.2:

$$\tilde{\Sigma}_{-l} = \left(\sum_{\substack{k=1 \\ k \neq l}}^L \hat{\Lambda}_k \right)^{-1} \quad (\text{Forward-Bayes})$$

$$= (\tilde{\Lambda}_L - \hat{\Lambda}_l)^{-1} \quad (\text{Reverse-Bayes})$$

$$\tilde{\beta}_{-l} = \tilde{\Sigma}_{-l} \sum_{\substack{k=1 \\ k \neq l}}^L \hat{\Lambda}_k \hat{\beta}_k \quad (\text{Forward-Bayes})$$

$$= \tilde{\Sigma}_{-l} [\tilde{\Lambda}_L \tilde{\beta}_L - \hat{\Lambda}_l \hat{\beta}_l] \quad (\text{Reverse-Bayes})$$

It is evident that the Forward-Bayes equation for $\tilde{\Sigma}_{-l}$ requires summing over $L - 1$ matrices, whereas the Reverse-Bayes approach requires only one matrix subtraction. In either case, the matrix $\tilde{\Lambda}_L$ has already been computed in a previous step, so there is no need to re-compute it for the Reverse-Bayes formula.

4.2. Linear regression

The Reverse-Bayes formulas for Λ_{-l} and a_{-l} can be immediately obtained from Equation 3.4. The derivations of β_{-l} and b_{-l} involve additional algebraic steps, which are shown in Appendix B. Here, we provide only the final expressions:

$$\beta_{-l} = \Lambda_{-l}^{-1} (\Lambda_L \beta_L - \mathbf{X}_l^\top \mathbf{y}_l)$$

$$\Lambda_{-l} = \sum_{\substack{k=1 \\ k \neq l}}^L \mathbf{X}_k^\top \mathbf{X}_k \quad (\text{Forward-Bayes})$$

$$= \Lambda_L - \mathbf{X}_l^\top \mathbf{X}_l \quad (\text{Reverse-Bayes})$$

$$a_{-l} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\substack{k=1 \\ k \neq l}}^L n_k - \frac{m+1}{2} = a_L - \frac{n_l}{2}$$

$$b_{-l} = b_L + \frac{1}{2} (\beta_L^\top \Lambda_L \beta_L - \beta_{-l}^\top \Lambda_{-l} \beta_{-l} - \mathbf{y}_l^\top \mathbf{y}_l).$$

Expressions for the other quantities can be obtained by inserting the above hyperparameters into their definitions, e.g. $\tau_{-l} = a_{-l}/b_{-l}$. For cross-validation or outlier assessment, these quantities must be computed for all L local sites. From the formulas for Λ_{-l} , it can be easily seen that the Forward-Bayes approach has a time complexity of $O(L^2 nm^2)$, whereas the Reverse-Bayes approach has a time complexity of $O(Lnm^2)$ (assuming a classical matrix multiplication algorithm).

4.3. Checking for conflicts among the sites

The Reverse-Bayes formulas provide a straightforward framework to quantify potential conflicts among the parameter estimates from the different local sites.¹⁶ To achieve this, we compute the prior-predictive tail probability p_{Box} using the formula from Box²² (see Appendix C):

$$p_{\text{Box}} = \Pr \left\{ F_{m+1, \nu_l + 2a_{-l}} > \frac{(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_l - \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{-l})^\top \{(\mathbf{X}_l^\top \mathbf{X}_l)^{-1} + \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_{-l}^{-1}\}^{-1} (\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_l - \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{-l})}{(m+1)s_p^2(\hat{\sigma}_l^2, \nu_l, a_{-l}, b_{-l})} \right\}.$$

The quantity s_p^2 is the pooled variance, seen as a function of the observed residual variance $\hat{\sigma}_l^2$, the degrees of freedom $\nu_l = n_l - m - 1$, and the reduced hyperparameters a_{-l} and b_{-l} . The probability p_{Box} corresponds to a standard analysis of variance test for the compatibility of two estimates $\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_l$ and $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{-l}$. It is called a prior-predictive tail probability because it gives the probability of observing data at least as extreme as the observed one under the predictive distribution implied by the specified prior. In our case, the posterior estimate $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{-l}$ obtained from all other sites serves as the prior estimate for site l . For better interpretability, we will use the binary Shannon information $s_{\text{Box}} = -\log_2 p_{\text{Box}}$ (also known as the S -value or surprisal value).²³ An S -value of $s_{\text{Box}} = h$ corresponds to the surprise of observing h consecutive heads among h tosses of a fair coin. A large s_{Box} indicates that the prior is a poor fit for the given data set. If only a few sites have large values of s_{Box} , these may represent outlier sites (possibly due to deviations from the prescribed analysis protocol or unaccounted heterogeneity). However, if many sites have large values of s_{Box} , this suggests that the model itself may be misspecified.

If the model includes site-specific intercepts, the symbols $\boldsymbol{\beta} \in \mathbb{R}^m$, $\mathbf{X}_l \in \mathbb{R}^{n_l \times m}$, and $\boldsymbol{\Lambda} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$ should be understood without the intercept terms. Moreover, the quantity $m + 1$ should be replaced by m , as we are only checking for conflicts in the covariate effects.

5. Methods and data

To compare the performance of the Bayesian conjugate analysis with the other methods, we reused two data sets included in the BFI package by Jonker, Pazira, and Coolen: `trauma`¹² (for logistic regression) and `nurses`¹³ (for linear regression). Following Jonker, Pazira, and Coolen, we standardized each numerical covariate by subtracting the mean from all data points and dividing by the standard deviation. We additionally generated a third synthetic data set, `nurses hom`, following a homogeneous linear model based on the `nurses` data set. We artificially included two outlier sites in this synthetic data set to demonstrate how our predictive checking method can detect such outliers.

5.1. Trauma data

This real-life data set consists of 371 data points from trauma patients in 12 hospitals.^{12;24} The outcome of interest is mortality (0 = survived, 1 = died) and the covariates are age (years), sex (0 = male, 1 = female), Injury Severity Score (ISS, ranging from 1 (low) to 75 (high)) and Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS, ranging from 3 (low) to 15 (high)). Although the specific hospital is not identified in the data set, each observation comes from one of three hospital types: a peripheral hospital without a neurosurgical unit (NSU), a peripheral hospital with an NSU, or an academic medical center. To simulate a federated inference scenario, we treat each hospital type as a local site whose data cannot be combined. As the patients originate from different hospital types, there may be heterogeneity in the distribution of outcome variable and covariates. To simulate a homogeneous setting, we therefore shuffle the patients while keeping the sample sizes of the three local sites fixed.

5.2. Nurses data

This simulated data set consists of 1000 data points representing nurses from 25 hospitals.^{13;25} The outcome of interest is job-related stress among nurses (ranging from 1 (low) to 7 (high)) and the covariates are age (years), experience (years), sex (0 = male, 1 = female), the type of ward in which the

nurse works (0 = general care, 1 = special care), and hospital (1, 2, . . . , 25). To simulate a federated inference scenario, we split the data according to the hospital.

5.3. Homogeneous nurses data

We generated an additional data set, `nurses hom`, based on the original `nurses` data set. We simulated data $(\mathbf{X}_l, \mathbf{y}_l)$ from a linear model

$$\mathbf{y}_l \sim N(\mathbf{X}_l \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}, \hat{\sigma}^2 \mathbf{I})$$

using parameters $\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}$ and $\hat{\sigma}^2$ obtained from fitting the `nurses` data on the combined data set with a global intercept (thus representing a homogeneous scenario). The covariates in \mathbf{X}_l were drawn from a standard normal distribution for numerical covariates (representing standardized age and experience) and from a binomial distribution with $p = 0.5$ for binary covariates (sex and ward type). The simulation was repeated $L = 25$ times, each representing a hospital with $n_l = 40$ nurses. Two hospitals were deliberately chosen as outliers: for hospital 24, the intercept $\hat{\beta}_0$ was increased by 1 to represent higher baseline stress levels; for hospital 25, the residual variance $\hat{\sigma}^2$ was doubled to simulate greater variability in stress measurements.

6. Results

In the following sections, we present regression parameters estimated from federated data using different methods: Bayesian Conjugate Analysis (BCA), distributed linear mixed models (DLMM), one-shot distributed algorithm to perform logistic regressions (ODAL), Bayesian Federated Inference (BFI), multivariate fixed-effect meta-analysis (FE), and multivariate random-effects meta-analysis with restricted maximum likelihood (REML). In addition, we performed ordinary GLM regressions on the combined data, treating the resulting parameter estimates as the ground truth. The federated estimates are then evaluated against these reference values. It is worth noting that the estimates we obtained using the BFI method on the `nurses` data sets numerically reproduce the results reported by the original authors of the package (Table 7 in Jonker, Pazira, and Coolen¹³). Moreover, for the FE and REML methods, we compute the residual variance σ^2 as the weighted mean of the local estimates, using the residual degrees of freedom as the weights.

6.1. Logistic regression

We present results for the homogeneous setting, that is, using a global intercept for all local sites. Figure 2 shows the parameter estimates $\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}$ for the `trauma` data set obtained with different methods (numeric values are available in Table 1 in the Supplementary Materials). A logistic regression model on the combined data is shown as a reference (ground truth) against which the other methods are compared. Panels A–E show the point estimates and 95% confidence intervals (resp. credible intervals) (CI) for the global intercept and the covariates GCS, ISS, age, and sex. Panel F shows the error of the respective point estimates with respect to the ground truth. Panel G shows the CI widths. As we used a non-informative prior for the BCA method, the estimates and CIs obtained are identical to the ones from the FE meta-analysis. In contrast, the BFI method requires non-zero priors, resulting in estimates that differ slightly from the BCA and FE estimates. REML performs slightly better than the methods discussed so far, but ODAL emerges as clearly the best method, with errors on the order of 10^{-4} .

Figure 2. Parameter estimates for logistic regression with the trauma dataset. Panels A–E: parameter estimates and 95% CIs. Panel F: error of parameter estimates relative to ground truth from the combined data. The error of the BCA and FE point estimates are identical. Panel G: Widths of CIs. The CIs for BCA and FE are also identical.

6.2. Linear regression

We present results for the homogeneous setting (that is, using a global intercept) in Figure 3 and for the heterogeneous setting (that is, allowing each local site to have a separate intercept) in Figure 4.

Figure 3 shows the parameter estimates $\hat{\beta}$ for the nurses data set obtained with different methods (numeric values are available in Table 2 in the Supplementary Materials). An ordinary linear regression model on the combined data is shown as a reference (ground truth) against which the other methods are compared. Panels A–F show the point estimates and 95% CIs for the covariates gender, age, and experience, as well as the residual variance σ^2 . Panel G shows the error of the respective point estimates with respect to the ground truth. Panel H shows the CI widths. The estimates and CIs obtained with BCA and DLMM are identical to the ones obtained with ordinary linear regression on the combined data, indicating lossless inference. The FE, REML, and BFI estimates all deviate from the ground truth, especially for the intercept, ward type, and residual variance. For comparison, we also analyzed this data set with the normal model from Section 3.1, rather than the linear regression model from Section 3.2. In that case, the resulting BCA estimates and CIs (not shown) are almost identical to the BFI estimates, as the two estimators are essentially identical (up to prior specification).

Figure 4 shows an analogous plots for the heterogeneous case with local intercepts for each site. The linear regression model on the combined data additionally uses the site identity as a categorical covariate. Wardtype is not used as a categorical variable to reproduce the analysis by Jonker, Pazira, and Coolen.¹³ Numeric values are available in Table 3 in the Supplementary Materials. The intercepts for the 25 hospitals are not included in the Figure and instead shown in Figure 1 in the Supplementary Materials. As in the previous case, BCA and DLMM work as intended and provide lossless estimation of covariate effects and uncertainty. The BFI, FE, and REML are not lossless; in particular, BFI severely underestimates σ^2 , producing far too short CIs and underestimating uncertainty.

Figure 3. Parameter estimates for linear regression with the nurses dataset using a global intercept. Panels A–F: parameter estimates and 95% CIs. The DLMM method does not compute CIs for σ^2 . Panel G: error of parameter estimates relative to ground truth from the combined data. Panel H: Widths of CIs.

Figure 4. Parameter estimates for linear regression with the nurses dataset using site-specific intercepts. Panels A–D: parameter estimates and 95% CIs. The DLMM method does not compute CIs for σ^2 . Panel E: error of parameter estimates relative to ground truth from the combined data. Panel F: Widths of CIs.

6.3. Predictive checking and outlier assessment

Figure 5 shows a scatter plot of $s_{\text{Box}} = -\log_2 p_{\text{Box}}$ vs. site identity for different analysis scenarios. A Bonferroni-corrected significance level of $\alpha = 0.05/25$ (corresponding to $s \approx 8.97$) is used to mark local sites as outliers. In Panel A, we show results for the nurses data set fitted using BCA with a global intercept (i.e., assuming homogeneity). We observe that 6 out of 25 sites exhibit large values of s_{Box} , suggesting unaccounted heterogeneity. Panel B shows the same analysis using local intercepts (i.e., assuming fixed-effects heterogeneity). Now, there are no more sites with large values of s_{Box} , suggesting that the previously identified outlier sites can be accommodated in this extended model. Panel C shows results for the nurses `hom` data set with two artificially introduced outlier sites, which are clearly identified by their large values of s_{Box} .

Figure 6 shows a multivariate forest plot generated by the `confer` package. Each panel corresponds to one covariate from the nurses `hom` data set (plots for the nurses data set are shown in the Supplementary Materials). Point estimates and 95% CIs are shown as green circles with error bars for site-specific estimates and as red diamonds for federated BCA estimates. The site-specific estimates were computed using summary statistics and single-site BCA. Values of s_{Box} are printed on the right of the figure. Values that pass a Bonferroni-corrected significance threshold of $p_{\text{Box}} < 0.05/25$ (resp. $s_{\text{Box}} > 8.97$) are shown in bold, which is the case for sites 24 and 25. From the respective parameter estimates, it can be easily seen that site 24 has a larger intercept than the other centers, while site 25 displays considerably wider CIs. This is consistent with the way the two sites were artificially constructed as outliers. In short, a multivariate forest plot offers an easy way to assess site-specific and overall results from a federated analysis, as well as to perform outlier checks.

Figure 5. Scatter plot of $s_{\text{Box}} = -\log_2 p_{\text{Box}}$ vs. site identity for different analysis scenarios. Values that pass a Bonferroni-corrected significance threshold of $p_{\text{Box}} < 0.05/25$ (dashed line) are shown in red.

Figure 6. Forest plot of local site estimates for all covariates (plus a global intercept) for the nurses hom data set. The red diamonds show the federated BCA estimates, with the CI given by the width of the diamonds. Values of $s_{\text{Box}} = -\log_2 p_{\text{Box}}$ are printed on the right. Values that pass a Bonferroni-corrected significance threshold of $p_{\text{Box}} < 0.05/25$ are shown in bold.

7. Discussion

We demonstrated the use of Bayesian conjugate analysis (BCA) in a federated inference setting. We showed that sequential Bayesian updating with conjugate priors leads to parallelizable one-shot formulas, that is, requiring only one round of independent communication between the local sites and the central server. We compared the performance of BCA with existing methods for federated inference, including meta-analytic, frequentist, and Bayesian approaches.

For models with asymptotically normal parameter estimates such as GLMs, we showed that using BCA with a normal model is, under assumptions of homogeneity, mathematically equivalent to a multivariate fixed-effect meta-analysis on the regression parameters (up to prior specification). For homogeneous settings, the BCA estimator is also equivalent to the Bayesian federated inference (BFI) estimator proposed by Jonker, Pazira, and Coolen. Thus, evaluation of the BCA method on a homogeneous logistic regression data set showed identical or near identical performance to BFI and multivariate meta-analysis. The one-shot privacy-preserving distributed algorithm to perform logistic regression (ODAL) performed best on the homogeneous data, with point estimates matching the combined-data ground truth to four significant digits. However, the current implementations of BCA (with the normal model) and ODAL do not yet support heterogeneity. Although an extended method, robust-ODAL²⁶, has been proposed to provide limited support for heterogeneity, it was not yet available in the pda package (version 1.2.8) when we tested it. A heterogeneity-aware BCA implementation supporting random effects for normal models is already planned, possibly using empirical Bayes to estimate between-site heterogeneity.²⁷

For the special case of linear regression, BCA can be applied using sufficient statistics, resulting in an exact, closed-form solution that is mathematically equivalent to performing ordinary least squares on the combined data set. Therefore, no information relevant to estimating the regression parameters

is lost in the federated setting, and there is no need for meta-analytic or approximate methods such as Bayesian Federated Inference (BFI). For non-informative priors, BCA is identical to the (frequentist) distributed linear mixed modeling (DLMM) algorithm with fixed effects.

One advantage of Bayesian methods is that they can incorporate prior knowledge. For example, if a prior study exists before the start of a new multi-center trial, the parameter estimates from that study can be used in place of a non-informative prior. If no data-driven priors are available, instead of the uninformative priors used in this manuscript, one could consider weakly-informative priors²⁸ that regularize estimation towards reasonable parameter values. For example, g -priors could be used in the linear model.²⁹

Another advantage of BCA is that it naturally lends itself to Reverse-Bayes analysis for computationally efficient predictive checks. Predictive checks are an important tool to perform model criticism²², that is, to measure the level of compatibility between the data, model, and prior. If the model is misspecified, it is not appropriate to combine the data and the prior into a posterior. In a federated setting, predictive checks on the homogeneous model can be used to assess the presence of heterogeneity and outlier sites. For the nurses data set, predictive checking on the homogeneous model identified 6/25 sites as incompatible with the model. Changing to a heterogeneous model with fixed intercepts for each site resulted in no more conflicts. For the nurses_hom data set, predictive checks successfully identified two artificially introduced outlier sites.

Both BCA and BFI can take into account heterogeneity through fixed-effects such as site-specific covariates, intercepts, and residual variances. However, only DLMM supports random-effects modeling, unlike the current implementations of BCA and BFI (the BFI authors state that random-effects models will be included in the future). When sites with small sample sizes are included, random-effects models may be more appropriate than fixed-effects models.^{30;4} Fixed effects cannot be used to generalize to new sites and run the danger of overfitting, particularly when some sites have limited data, although in Bayesian approaches, it is possible to regularize such overfitting by using weakly-informative shrinkage priors. Nevertheless, partial pooling via random effects may provide better estimates and supports generalization beyond the observed sites. For Bayesian generalized linear mixed models, closed-form inference is generally not available.³¹ However, in the special case of Bayesian linear mixed models, one can exploit conditional conjugacy by placing an inverse-Wishart prior on the random-effects covariance matrix and using numerical methods to perform posterior inference.³² Alternatively, the covariance matrix can be decomposed into a scale and a correlation matrix with a (non-conjugate) LKJ prior.³³ Future extensions of our work could explore the practical feasibility of these approaches in a federated inference setting. The BCA framework as described in this article is implemented in the open-source `confeR` package (conjugate federated analysis in R), including Reverse-Bayes predictive checks and visualization using multivariate forest plots.

A. Residual variance for Bayesian linear regression

In Bayesian linear regression, we use the inverse of the mean $\tau_L = a_L/b_L$ of the marginal gamma distribution to estimate the residual variance. For non-informative priors, this choice aligns with the estimator provided by the classical ordinary least squares (OLS) model, which is given by

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{\sigma}^2 &= \frac{1}{n-m-1} (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{X}\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}})^\top (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{X}\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}) \\ &= \frac{1}{n-m-1} (\mathbf{y}^\top \mathbf{y} - 2\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}^\top \mathbf{X}^\top \mathbf{y} + \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}^\top \mathbf{X}^\top \mathbf{X}\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}) \\ &= \frac{1}{n-m-1} (\mathbf{y}^\top \mathbf{y} - \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}^\top \mathbf{X}^\top \mathbf{X}\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}).\end{aligned}$$

The last equation follows from the fact that $\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}$ is the OLS estimator. The posterior hyperparameters of the gamma distribution are

$$\begin{aligned} a_L &= n/2 - (m + 1)/2 \\ b_L &= \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{y}^\top \mathbf{y} - \boldsymbol{\beta}_L^\top \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_L \boldsymbol{\beta}_L) \\ &= \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{y}^\top \mathbf{y} - \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}^\top \mathbf{X}^\top \mathbf{X} \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}). \end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_L^2 &= \tau_L^{-1} \\ &= \frac{b_L}{a_L} \\ &= \frac{\mathbf{y}^\top \mathbf{y} - \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}^\top \mathbf{X}^\top \mathbf{X} \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}}{2(n/2 - (m + 1)/2)} \\ &= \frac{1}{n - m - 1}(\mathbf{y}^\top \mathbf{y} - \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}^\top \mathbf{X}^\top \mathbf{X} \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}) \\ &= \hat{\sigma}^2. \end{aligned}$$

B. Reverse-Bayes hyperparameters for linear regression

We derive formulas for the Reverse-Bayes hyperparameters $\boldsymbol{\beta}_{-l}$ and b_{-l} . From the formula for $\boldsymbol{\beta}_L$ in Equation 3.4, we obtain

$$\sum_{\substack{k=1 \\ k \neq l}}^L \mathbf{X}_k^\top \mathbf{y}_k = \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_L \boldsymbol{\beta}_L - \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_0 \boldsymbol{\beta}_0 - \mathbf{X}_l^\top \mathbf{y}_l.$$

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\beta}_{-l} &= \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_{-l}^{-1}(\boldsymbol{\Lambda}_0 \boldsymbol{\beta}_0 + \sum_{\substack{k=1 \\ k \neq l}}^L \mathbf{X}_k^\top \mathbf{y}_k) \\ &= \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_{-l}^{-1}(\boldsymbol{\Lambda}_0 \boldsymbol{\beta}_0 + \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_L \boldsymbol{\beta}_L - \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_0 \boldsymbol{\beta}_0 - \mathbf{X}_l^\top \mathbf{y}_l) \\ &= \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_{-l}^{-1}(\boldsymbol{\Lambda}_L \boldsymbol{\beta}_L - \mathbf{X}_l^\top \mathbf{y}_l). \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, from the formula for b_L in Equation 3.4, we obtain:

$$\frac{1}{2} \sum_{\substack{k=1 \\ k \neq l}}^L \mathbf{y}_k^\top \mathbf{y}_k = b_L - b_0 - \frac{1}{2}(\boldsymbol{\beta}_0^\top \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_0 \boldsymbol{\beta}_0 - \boldsymbol{\beta}_L^\top \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_L \boldsymbol{\beta}_L + \mathbf{y}_l^\top \mathbf{y}_l).$$

Inserting this into our formula for b_{-l} , we get:

$$\begin{aligned}
b_{-l} &= b_0 + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\substack{k=1 \\ k \neq l}}^L \mathbf{y}_k^\top \mathbf{y}_k + \frac{1}{2} (\boldsymbol{\beta}_0^\top \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_0 \boldsymbol{\beta}_0 - \boldsymbol{\beta}_{-l}^\top \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_{-l} \boldsymbol{\beta}_{-l}) \\
&= b_0 + b_L - b_0 - \frac{1}{2} (\boldsymbol{\beta}_0^\top \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_0 \boldsymbol{\beta}_0 - \boldsymbol{\beta}_L^\top \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_L \boldsymbol{\beta}_L + \mathbf{y}_l^\top \mathbf{y}_l) + \frac{1}{2} (\boldsymbol{\beta}_0^\top \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_0 \boldsymbol{\beta}_0 - \boldsymbol{\beta}_{-l}^\top \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_{-l} \boldsymbol{\beta}_{-l}) \\
&= b_L + \frac{1}{2} (\boldsymbol{\beta}_L^\top \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_L \boldsymbol{\beta}_L - \boldsymbol{\beta}_{-l}^\top \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_{-l} \boldsymbol{\beta}_{-l} - \mathbf{y}_l^\top \mathbf{y}_l).
\end{aligned}$$

C. Prior-predictive tail distribution

We follow the methodology described in Section 3 of Box.²² The prior distribution of the residual variance σ^2 is parametrized using a scaled inverse chi-squared distribution with parameters ν_0 (degrees of freedom) and s_0^2 (scale parameter). This is a special case of the inverse-gamma distribution:

$$\begin{aligned}
\sigma^2 &\sim \text{Scale-}\chi^{-2}(\nu_0, s_0^2) \\
&\sim \text{Inv-Gamma}\left(\frac{\nu_0}{2}, \frac{\nu_0 s_0^2}{2}\right).
\end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$\lambda = \sigma^{-2} \sim \text{Gamma}(a_0 = \frac{\nu_0}{2}, b_0 = \frac{\nu_0 s_0^2}{2}).$$

Therefore, we identify $\nu_0 = 2a_0$ and $s_0^2 = b_0/a_0$. Now, let $\nu = n - m - 1$. We define the pooled variance

$$\begin{aligned}
s_p^2(\sigma^2, \nu, a_0, b_0) &= (\nu + \nu_0)^{-1} (\nu \sigma^2 + \nu_0 s_0^2) \\
&= (\nu + 2a_0)^{-1} (\nu \sigma^2 + 2b_0).
\end{aligned}$$

Its observed value is $\hat{s}_p^2 = s_p^2(\hat{\sigma}^2, \nu, a_0, b_0)$, where $\hat{\sigma}^2$ the observed residual variance as defined in Appendix A. Finally, we rewrite Box's predictive check in terms of our notation:

$$\begin{aligned}
p_{\text{Box}} &= \Pr\{p((\boldsymbol{\beta} - \boldsymbol{\beta}_0)/s_p^2 | A) < p((\tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}} - \boldsymbol{\beta}_0)/\hat{s}_p^2 | A)\} \\
&= \Pr\left\{F_{m+1, \nu+2a_0} > \frac{(\tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}} - \boldsymbol{\beta}_0)^\top \{(\mathbf{X}^\top \mathbf{X})^{-1} + \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_0^{-1}\}^{-1} (\tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}} - \boldsymbol{\beta}_0)}{(m+1)\hat{s}_p^2}\right\}.
\end{aligned}$$

As explained in Box,²² A is understood to indicate conditionality on all or some of the assumptions in the model specification. The second line is the standard analysis of variance test for compatibility of two estimates $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}$ and $\boldsymbol{\beta}_0$, using the corresponding F -statistic. Following Held et al.,¹⁵ we compute a prior-predictive tail probability for each site-specific estimate $\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_l$, with a prior based on the remaining sites $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{-l}$:

$$p_{\text{Box}} = \Pr\left\{F_{m+1, \nu_l+2a_{-l}} > \frac{(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_l - \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{-l})^\top \{(\mathbf{X}_l^\top \mathbf{X}_l)^{-1} + \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_{-l}^{-1}\}^{-1} (\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_l - \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{-l})}{(m+1)s_p^2(\hat{\sigma}_l^2, \nu_l, a_{-l}, b_{-l})}\right\}.$$

D. Code example for confeR package

Below, we provide an example code snippet to perform BCA linear regression with the `confeR` package, using the built-in `nurses_hom` data set.

```
## CRAN version TBA
## install.packages("confeR")

## Or: Install development version from GitLab
install.packages("remotes")
remotes::install_gitlab(repo = "crsuzh/confeR", subdir = "package", host = "gitlab.uzh.ch")

library(confeR)

# Load data: list of summary statistics (X'X, X'y, y'y, n) for each site
data(nurses_hom, package = "confeR")
sumstats <- nurses_hom$summary_stats

# Option to fit separate intercepts for each site (no global intercept)
use_local_intercepts <- TRUE

# Perform one-shot estimation with local intercepts
params_oneshot <- bca_oneshot(sumstats, use_local_intercepts, family="gaussian")

# Summarize results as dataframe
df_bca <- tidy_results(params_oneshot, use_local_intercepts)

# Compute predictive check
pred_results <- pred_check(params_oneshot,
                           sumstats,
                           family="gaussian",
                           use_local_intercepts=TRUE)

# Make forest plot
forest_box(params_oneshot,
           sumstats,
           family="gaussian",
           use_local_intercepts=TRUE,
           alpha=0.05)
```

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Data Availability Statement. A GitLab repository with the full code and software environment specification to reproduce the analysis is available from <https://gitlab.uzh.ch/crsuzh/confeR>. The Bayesian conjugate analyses were implemented in base R (version 4.3.3) and made available in the `confeR` (conjugate federated analysis) package, which also contains the `nurses_hom` data set. The BFI analyses were performed using the `BFI`¹² R package, which also contains the `trauma` and `nurses` data sets. The multivariate meta-analyses were performed using the `metafor`³⁴ R package. DLMM and ODAL analyses were performed using the `pda`² R package.

Ethical Standards. The research meets all ethical guidelines, including adherence to the legal requirements of the study country.

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